

Studies on Oxofluoroniobates and Oxofluoroniobic Acids

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The results of conductometric and thermometric titrations of the system potassium hexaniobate-acid (HA), where $A = F^-$, ClO_4^- , $ClCH_2COO^-$ and CH_3COO^- , suggest the formation of $H_2Nb_5O_{19}^{2-}$ and $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 4H_2O$. These studies with HF suggest also the formation of $NbOF_5^-$ and $HNbOF_5^-$. The system $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O - M^+HF_n$, where $M = NH_4^+$, Na^+ and K^+ , was investigated through preparative methods and a general suitable method for the preparation of oxohexafluoroniobates of NH_4^+ , Na^+ and K^+ is described. A similar reaction with $RbHF_4$ results in the formation of Rb_2NbOF_5 . A method for the preparation of $[Co(NH_3)_6][NbOF_5] \cdot H_2O$ is described. The TGA and IR data of sodium and hexamminecobalt (III) salts are reported.

The acids H_2NbOF_5 (aq.) and H_2NbOF_6 (aq.) generated by passing the solutions of K_2NbOF_5 and K_3NbOF_6 through cation exchange resin columns are studied by conductometry, thermometry and potentiometry. The pK_a values for H_2NbOF_5 and H_3NbOF_6 are found to be 2.82 and 2.96 respectively.

NUMEROUS physico-chemical studies were made to show the formation of various fluoroniobate species in solution¹⁻⁵. From potentiometric study of the system Nb(V) - OH^- - F^- in KCl (3M) Neumann⁸ suggested the formation of $Nb(OH)_2F_4^-$ and $Nb(OH)_2F_5^{2-}$. From a study of Raman spectra of solutions of K_2NbF_7 in aqueous HF at various concentrations Keller⁴ inferred that $NbOF_5^{2-}$ dominates in 0-11 M HF, whereas NbF_6^- prevails at higher concentrations of HF. Land and Osborne⁵ extensively studied the stepwise formation of various oxofluoroniobium and fluoroniobate species, viz. $NbOF_3$, $NbOF_4^-$, $NbOF_5^{2-}$ etc., which existed in solutions of various ranges of acid, metal and fluoride ion concentrations. In the present work the decondensation of hexaniobate ion, $Nb_6O_{19}^{2-}$, and the formation of various fluoroniobate species are studied through conductometric and thermometric titrations of hexaniobate by HF. For comparison similar titrations were also made with several other acids, viz. $HClO_4$, CH_3COOH and $ClCH_2COOH$.

Alkali metal and ammonium oxopenta- and oxohexafluoroniobates are usually prepared by recrystallisation of corresponding heptafluoroniobates and through rigorous control of HF and M^+F^- concentrations in relation to the concentration of niobium⁶⁻¹⁰, and no direct simple method is known for their preparation. The present workers made a study of the system, $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O - M^+HF_n$, where $M^+ = NH_4^+$, Na^+ , K^+ and Rb^+ at the various ratios of reactants through preparative methods. A general simple method for the preparation of ammonium, sodium and potassium oxohexafluoroniobates has thus been found out and reported here. Besides, a method for the preparation of hexamminecobalt (III) oxohexafluoroniobate and its TGA and IR data alongwith those for the corresponding sodium compound are reported.

Niobium pentoxide dissolves readily in HF, but evaporation of the solution leaves an insoluble white residue consisting mostly of the oxide^{6,7}. Free

fluoroniobic acid has not been isolated and their aqueous solutions have also not been studied. From the solution phase analysis of the (i) Nb_2O_5 in HF and (ii) Nb_2O_5 and NbO_2F in HNO_3 - HF acids Ferris¹ suggested the existence of H_2NbOF_5 . In the present work the two oxofluoroniobic acids, viz. H_2NbOF_5 and H_3NbOF_6 , generated from the corresponding potassium oxofluoroniobates with the help of cation exchange resin, were studied through conductometric, thermometric and pH-titrations.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the present work were of reagent quality, and the usual standard methods for the analyses were followed¹¹.

Conductometric and thermometric titrations of potassium hexaniobate by acid: For preparing potassium hexaniobate $K_6Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$, a mixture (1:5) of Nb_2O_5 and K_2CO_3 was fused by a Meker burner. The melt was taken into hot water and the undissolved materials were filtered off. The desired product was obtained from the above solution by adding a saturated solution of potassium acetate. The moderately soluble needle-shaped crystals were filtered off by suction, washed with absolute alcohol, dried in air and analysed. (Found K_2O 25.73, Nb_2O_5 55.13 and H_2O 19.68%. $K_6Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ requires K_2O 25.67, Nb_2O_5 54.53% and H_2O 19.71%). A stock solution of hexaniobate was not used for the conductometric and thermometric titrations since turbidity appeared on prolonged standing of the solution. Hence fresh solutions were made for each titration by dissolving known weights of hexaniobate in known volumes of CO_2 -free conductivity water.

HF and other acid solutions were standardised by the usual standard methods. The fluoride and HF solutions were preserved in polythene bottles. Calibrated polythene burette and pipette were used for the measurement of HF solutions.

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration of potassium hexaniobate by HF at 29.5°C. Curve I. X represents the conductance of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.003 \times 10^{-4}M$); Y represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 100 ml water by hydrofluoric acid (0.2055M); Z denotes the conductance recorded in the titration of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.003 \times 10^{-4}M$) by hydrofluoric acid (0.2055M). Curve II. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($1.832 \times 10^{-3}M$) by hydrofluoric acid (0.3809M).

Fig. 2. Conductometric titration of potassium hexaniobate by perchloric acid, chloroacetic acid and acetic acid at 29.5°C. Curve I. X represents the conductance of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.29 \times 10^{-4}M$); Y represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 100 ml water by $HClO_4$ (0.1945M); Z denotes the conductance recorded in the titration of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.29 \times 10^{-4}M$) by $HClO_4$ (0.1945M). Curve II. X, Y and Z, have the same significance as above in the titration of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.003 \times 10^{-4}M$) by chloroacetic acid (0.1945M). Curve III. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 100 ml $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($7.49 \times 10^{-4}M$) by acetic acid (0.2245M).

The conductance of solutions were measured with a Philips Conductivity Bridge No. PR 9500. A conductivity cell containing dip type platinum electrodes fitted in polythene stems was used. For each of the conductometric titration systems consisting of hexaniobate and acid two titrations were performed at the same temperature, viz. (a) a known volume (x ml) of standard potassium hexaniobate solution (its conductance denoted as X) was titrated conductometrically (conductance of mixtures denoted as Z) by a standard acid, and (b) a known volume (x ml) of water was titrated conductometrically (conductance values denoted as Y) by the same standard acid utilized in the above titration. The change of conductance of the potassium hexaniobate solutions due to dilution was found to be so small that it does not alter the shape of the difference curve at all and hence instead of using these values the conductance of the hexaniobate solution X before titration was utilized in the calculations. The difference of the conductance values (X + Y - Z) were plotted against molar ratio $[Acid]/[Hexaniobate]$, and the results are reported in Figs. 1 & 2.

A thermometric titration of potassium hexaniobate by HF was carried out as before^{1,2} and the temperature change at a constant volume (T_v) was plotted (Fig. 3) against the molar ratio of HF to $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$.

Preparative study of $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O - M^IHF_2$, where $M^I = NH_4^+, Na^+, K^+$ and Rb^+ : Several sets of mixtures of $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ and M^IHF_2 were made at the ratios $Nb_2O_5 : M^IHF_2 = 1 : 4, 1 : 6$ and $1 : 10$ and crystallized as described below. The results are reported in Table 1. Hydrated niobium pentoxide, $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$, was precipitated by passing excess of ammonia gas through a solution of Nb_2O_5 in HF. The

Fig. 3. Thermometric titration of $K_8Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ ($1.84 \times 10^{-3} M$) by HF (0.4039M).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF THE PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM THE REACTIONS BETWEEN $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ AND MHF_3 , WHERE $M = NH_4^+, Na^+, K^+$ and Rb^+ .

System	Molar ratio	Found					
$Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ — NH_4HF_3	1 : 4	% N	15.43	% Nb	34.00	% F	41.75
"	1 : 6.4		15.10		34.17		41.07
"	1 : 10		14.75		32.57		41.17
$Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ — KHF_3	1 : 4		—		27.81		33.75
"	1 : 6	% K	34.63		27.70		33.39
"	1 : 10		—		27.59		32.48
$Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ — $NaHF_2$	1 : 4	% Na	22.49		30.27		37.63
"	1 : 7		28.03		30.77		40.58
"	1 : 10		—		19.84		46.40
$Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O$ — $RbHF_3$	1 : 6	% Rb	44.2		24.04		24.60
$(NH_4)_3NbOF_6$	requires	N	15.17, Nb	33.55 and F	41.17 %		
K_3NbOF_6	requires	K	34.42, Nb	27.33 and F	33.54 %		
$Na_3NbOF_6 \cdot 0.5H_2O$	requires	Na	22.93, Nb	30.87 and F	37.88 %		
$Rb_3NbOF_6 \cdot 0.5H_2O$	requires	Rb	44.32, Nb	24.60 and F	24.75 %		

precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and utilised. The hydrated oxide was placed in a small volume of water and to it calculated amount of a bifluoride solution was added. The mixture was heated over water bath for about half an hour and was filtered. The clear filtrate was evaporated on a water bath to crystallization. After cooling the crystals were filtered off, pressed between folds of filter paper, dried in a vacuum desiccator containing KOH and H_2SO_4 and analysed¹¹.

Hexaamminecobalt (III) oxohexafluoronioabate monohydrate : It was obtained as a yellow precipitate through the dropwise addition of hexaamminecobalt(III)

chloride (1.3 g.), dissolved in minimum volume of water to a solution of potassium oxohexafluoronioabate (1.7 g.) also dissolved in minimum volume of water. The polyhedral crystals were filtered by suction, washed with water, filter-pressed between the folds of filter paper and finally dried in air. Yield 1 g. (Analysis : Found N 20.42, Nb 22.82 and F 28.16% ; $[Co(NH_3)_6][NbOF_6] \cdot H_2O$ requires N 20.96, Nb 23.12 and F 28.37%). The compound is insoluble in water and hydrolyses on boiling. The TGA data (Fig. 4) of the compound carried out in a manually operated thermobalance as before¹⁸ show that the compound starts decomposing from 50°C and its rapid decomposition takes place in the range 300-350°C.

Fig. 4. TGA data of (a) $\text{Na}_3\text{NbOF}_6 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{NbOF}_6] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

IR-spectra : The spectra of $\text{Na}_3\text{NbOF}_6 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{NbOF}_6] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were recorded in KBr pellet in the region $700\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The data along with probable band assignments are reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRA (IN cm^{-1}) OF $\text{Na}_3\text{NbOF}_6 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (I) AND $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{NbOF}_6] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (II).

I	II	Probable band assignment
743-745 (b, m)	—	—
930 (s)	880 (s)	$\nu_{\text{Nb-O}}$
—	997 (w)	—
—	1115-1138 (b, w)	—
—	1325 (s)	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$
—	1370 (m, sh)	—
1415 (w)	—	—
1640-1685 (b, w)	1600-1640 (b, s)	$\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
1875 (m)	—	—
—	3275 (s, sh)	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$
3400-3550 (b, m)	3350 (s)	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, sh=shoulder, b=broad

Preparation of aqueous solutions of H_2NbOF_6 and H_3NbOF_6 and their studies : A resin column made of polythene was packed with Amberlite IR-120 (H^+ form) and a known amount of K_3NbOF_6 (prepared as described in a previous section) dissolved in water was passed through the column and the effluent and washing were collected together in a polythene container. The effluent was found to be free from K^+ ion. On analysing for Nb and F the ratio of Nb : F in the effluent was found to be 1 : 6. These results suggested the presence of H_3NbOF_6 in the effluent. Aqueous H_2NbOF_6 was prepared in the same manner as above starting from K_3NbOF_6 which was prepared^{1,4} from K_2NbF_7 . The evaporation of the acids in a desiccator did not produce any crystals of the corresponding acids, and in both the cases white insoluble materials containing niobium and little fluorine were left.

The conductometric and thermometric titrations (Figs. 5 & 6) of the acids were performed as described in a previous section. The potentiometric titrations (Fig. 7) of the acids by alkali were carried out with a Philips precision pH-meter (Model PR 9405 M) using glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode. The salt bridge used for the pH measurements was made of a polythene tube filled with NaNO_3 (1 M) in agar agar. The glass electrode was tested by measuring pH of standard buffer solutions before and after the titrations of the oxo-fluoroniobic acids. The reproducibility of the electrode was found not to be affected by the dilute acids. The pK values of the two acids are graphically obtained by applying Bjerrum's method^{1,5}. In the

Fig. 5. Conductometric titration of H_2NbOF_6 and H_3NbOF_6 by KOH at 29°C .

Curve I. X represents the conductance recorded on adding KOH (0.1532M) to 40 ml water; Y represents the conductance recorded on diluting 40 ml H_2NbOF_6 ($3.742 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) by water; Z denotes the conductance recorded in the titration of 40 ml H_2NbOF_6 ($3.742 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) by KOH (0.1532M).

Curve II. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 40 ml H_3NbOF_6 ($4.742 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) by KOH ($5.934 \times 10^{-2}\text{M}$).

Curve III & IV. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of (i) 40 ml of H_2NbOF_6 ($3.75 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) by KOH ($5.70 \times 10^{-2}\text{M}$) and (ii) 40 ml H_3NbOF_6 ($3.75 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) by KOH ($8.19 \times 10^{-2}\text{M}$) respectively.

case of H_2NbOF_6 the values of \bar{n} (average number of hydrogen ion bound to the complex anion) are calculated from the relation

$$\bar{n} = \frac{2A - P - [\text{H}^+]}{A}$$

Fig. 6. Thermometric titrations of (Curve I) 100 ml H_2NbOF_5 ($9.23 \times 10^{-3} M$) by KOH ($0.2757 M$) and (Curve II) 100 ml H_2NbOF_6 ($1.573 \times 10^{-3} M$) by KOH ($0.2789 M$).

Fig. 8. \bar{n} -pH plot of the titrations (as referred in Fig. 7) of (i) H_2NbOF_5 by $NaOH$ (Curve I) and (ii) H_2NbOF_6 by $NaOH$ (Curve II).

Fig. 7. Potentiometric titrations of (i) 100 ml H_2NbOF_5 ($5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$) by $NaOH$ ($0.1 M$) (Curve I) and (ii) 100 ml H_2NbOF_6 ($2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$) by $NaOH$ ($0.1 M$) at $22.5^\circ C$. All solutions were maintained at $0.5 M$ with respect to $NaClO_4$.

where A =total concentration of the complex acid taken, and P =the concentration of alkali added at any stage of the titration. In a similar manner \bar{n} values in the case of H_2NbOF_6 are calculated from the relation

$$\bar{n} = \frac{3A - P - [H^+]}{A}$$

The different pK values for the two acids are then obtained from the plot of \bar{n} vs. pH (Fig. 8).

Discussion

The conductometric titrations of potassium hexaniobate by acetic acid (HAc), chloroacetic acid ($ClAcH$) and perchloric acid show breaks corresponding to the reacting ratios $Nb_6O_{19}^{6-} : HA$, where $A=Ac^-$, $ClAc^-$ and ClO_4^- , at 1 : 2 and 1 : 8, whereas, conductometric titration of potassium hexaniobate by HF shows breaks at the above ratios and also at 1 : 26 and 1 : 32. But through thermometric titration of hexaniobate by HF only breaks at 1 : 8, 1 : 26 and 1 : 32 are observed. During the conductometric titrations it was noticed that hydrated niobic acid gets precipitated at the 1 : 8 ratio of hexaniobate : HA . It might be presumed that the breaks obtained at hexaniobate : acid=1 : 2 and 1 : 8 are probably due to the formation of $H_2Nb_6O_{19}^{6-}$ and $H_8Nb_6O_{19}$ (or $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 4H_2O$). Only in the case of hexaniobate- HF system, however, gradual dissolution of hydrated niobic pentoxide by HF takes place probably due to the successive formation of $NbOF_4$ and $HNbOF_5$ as indicated by inflection points corresponding to hexaniobate : $HF=1 : 26$ and 1 : 32. Attempts for the isolation of potassium oxotetrafluoronioabate and the acid oxopentafluoronioabate by crystallising a mixture of potassium hexaniobate and HF at the above two ratios, however, failed and in each case the analytical results of the isolated filter-pressed product corresponded approximately to $Nb : F$ ratio 1 : 4.5.

The preparative study of $Nb_2O_5 \cdot xH_2O - M^IHF_2$ indicated that hydrated niobic pentoxide dissolved completely in KHF_2 , NH_4HF_2 and $NaHF_2$ at 1 : 6, 1 : 6.4 and 1 : 7 respectively. The analytical results (Table 1) for the products obtained at the above three ratios utilising NH_4HF_2 and KHF_2 show the formation of $(NH_4)_3NbOF_6$ and K_3NbOF_6 . But Na_3NbOF_6 could be obtained only at 1 : 4, whilst at the higher ratios of $NaHF_2$ the products remain contaminated with NaF . Similar reaction as above utilizing $RbHF_2$ at 1 : 6, however, produced Rb_2NbOF_6 .

From a study of IR spectra of $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{NbOF}_6$ and K_3NbOF_6 , the Nb=O stretching frequency has been reported at 910 cm^{-1} and 922 cm^{-1} respectively for the two compounds.^{1,6,17,18} In the present work the strong band for Nb=O was found at 930 cm^{-1} and 880 cm^{-1} respectively for the sodium and hexaamminecobalt(II) oxohexafluoroniobates. A broad medium band found in the region $3400\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the sodium compound and a strong band at 3350 cm^{-1} for the hexaamminecobalt(III) compound correspond to the O-H stretching band for water. In the latter case the superimposition of the band due to N-H is also possible. Besides, bands at 3275 cm^{-1} and 1390 cm^{-1} due to N-H are found for the hexaamminecobalt(III) compound. In the case of sodium and hexaamminecobalt(III) compounds the deformation band for water appeared in the region $1640\text{--}1685\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1600\text{--}1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

The TGA data (Fig. 4) for $\text{Na}_3\text{NbOF}_6 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not show the formation of the anhydrous compound. The loss in weight (13.45%) at 600°C agrees well with the generation of NaF and Nb_2O_5 from the compound. In the case of hexaamminecobalt(III) compound slow decomposition starts from 50°C probably due to the loss of water and thereafter rapid decomposition due to loss of NH_3 is observed.

The conductometric titration (Fig. 5) of oxopentafluoroniobic acid (H_3NbOF_6) by potassium hydroxide show two inflection points corresponding to the first and second neutralisation points of the acid. Similar titration of H_3NbOF_6 show only two inflection points corresponding to the first and second neutralisation points of the acid.

The thermometric titration (Fig. 6) of H_3NbOF_6 by KOH show only one break corresponding to the second neutralisation point of the acid, whilst a similar titration of H_3NbOF_6 indicate also one break corresponding to the second neutralisation point of the acid. It may be mentioned here that the precipitation of $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ takes place just before the second neutralisation point of H_3NbOF_6 , and in the case of H_3NbOF_6 the same phenomenon is observed just after the second stoichiometric end point. These observations are in agreement with the results of conductometric and thermometric titrations of the two acids.

The potentiometric titration data (Fig. 7) of both the acids show slow rise in pH, but no sharp rise in pH is observed at any of the stoichiometric neutralisation points. The pK_1 value for H_3NbOF_6 could not be found since at pH 2.23 (Fig. 8) the value of \bar{n} is calculated to be 0.82, which is far below 1.5 the value

to give the pK_1 value of the acid. From the graph the pK_2 value corresponding to $\bar{n}=0.5$ is found to be 2.82. Similarly from the n-pH curve of H_3NbOF_6 the pK_1 value of the acid cannot be obtained since at the start of the titration the value of \bar{n} , corresponding to pH 2.65, is found to be 1.88, which is below 2.5, the value to furnish the pK_1 of the acid. From the graph the pK_2 value corresponding to $\bar{n}=1.5$ is found to be 2.96. The pK_3 value of the acid has not been calculated in a similar way, since the precipitation of $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ occurs just after the second stoichiometric end point indicating the unstable character of NbOF_6^{3-} at a higher pH.

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